

**PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGY-BASED APPROACH
TO MASTERING THE CONTENT OF "MUSIC
CULTURE" LESSONS**

Department of Music Education, Termiz State
Pedagogical Institute
Karimova, 2nd year graduate student
Maksuda Rustamovna

Abstract. This article is about music lessons in secondary schools explores different forms of organization, the effectiveness of different approaches and studies the effect. By analyzing the available literature, this research is applied methodologies, their outcomes, and their potential impact on student music education aimed at giving for understanding it.

Key words: music education, comprehensive schools, organizational models, teaching methodology, curriculum, student engagement.

Today, the spiritual maturity of the youth, who are the foundation of our country, is one of the urgent issues. The art of music is of particular importance in bringing out the talents of young people, in their spiritual formation, and in their spiritual maturity.

"Speaking about the spiritual maturity of a person, of course, this goal cannot be achieved without the art of music," says our president I.A. Karimov, "today, the art of music has a greater and stronger influence than other forms of art on the development of our modern generation in the spirit of high spirituality." Music art is a unique world. It is a world of wonderful sounds, charming melodies and emotional experiences. Music is an art that reflects a person's feelings, experiences, thoughts, life ideas and reality in unique ways. By affecting the heart, soul, and emotions of the listener, it develops various abilities, develops consciousness and thinking, and helps to perceive life in a wider and deeper way.

It is known that one of the most important issues of Eastern philosophy has been perfect human education. Therefore, in the process of approaching music from a philosophical point of view, its place in the improvement of the human spirit is first of all important. Scholars of the past have always emphasized the incomparable importance of the art of music in the formation of a person as a person, its divinity, and its connection with the psyche. The true founder of the science of music, the great lexicographer of the Middle Ages, Abu Nasr al-Farabi, makes a scientific assessment of the origin of music and emphasizes that music is multi-functional: a source of pleasure, a means of entertainment, and a means of spiritual education. In each says that music becomes a means of influencing the listener and this is the first factor for music to live as art. Therefore, the search for and improvement of the means of musical influence has become an important task of music science for Farabi. Ibn Sina, the great thinker of the East, was one of the first scientists to justify the educational importance of music in the development of personality. In his views on musical education, he mentions that through music, it is connected with the formation and development of the human spirit and the training of the body with physical exercises, that is, it has a healing effect on the body together with the soul.

The concept of pedagogical technology is a broad, versatile concept that serves the practice of effective development of human potential. The content, goals and tasks, tools and methods, forms of pedagogical activity are expanding and improving according to the needs of the times. This field has begun to follow a holistic system, i.e. technology, which enables the full implementation of educational goals envisaged by the development of our modern society.

As a result of our study of scientific literature on the problem of pedagogical technologies, we can conclude as follows:

At the current stage of development of education, the need to update teaching methods, tools and forms of organization is increasing. This problem is

closely related to the development of modern pedagogical technologies and their inclusion in the educational process.

Ped. the main purpose of technologies is to organize the interdependent activity of the teacher and the student and direct it to ensure the planned results.

The main features of these technologies are:

- setting specific goals and tasks for the students, personal understanding of the studied material by each student, motivation of the student's educational activities;

- structuring the stages of achieving goals and tasks with the help of specific tools, active methods and forms of organization;

- teaching with samples and examples (according to the textbook);

- fulfilling the teacher's task;

- organization of independent work of students aimed at solving problematic educational tasks;

- use of various forms of control aimed at checking educational results.

Uzbek scientist B. L. Faberman defines pedagogical technology as follows: "Pedagogical technology is a new (innovative) approach to the educational process, social engineering in pedagogy is an expression of consciousness. It is a social phenomenon related to the creation of its optimal project by standardizing the pedagogical process on the basis of technical capabilities and human technical thinking.

Russian scientist, academician V.P. Bespalko gives a scientific definition of this concept, based on the ways of applying this pedagogical innovation to the teaching process:

"Pedagogical technology is a project of the process of formation of the personality of the student, which can guarantee pedagogical success, regardless of the skills of the teacher."

According to the definition of M. Choshanov: "Educational technology is a component-process part of the didactic system"

The structural structure of pedagogical technologies consists of a conceptual basis, a substantive part (the purpose of teaching, the content of educational methods) and procedural parts (organization of the educational process, methods and forms of student learning activities, methods and forms of teacher activity, evaluation of training results, etc.). One of the pedagogical approaches as a conceptual basis of pedagogical technology: person-oriented, programmatic, developmental education, etc. can come out. The selected pedagogical approach determines the goals, content and methods, tools, methods and forms of pedagogical technology.

Pedagogical technology is defined differently, but its essence can be understood as a complex of interrelated components that enable the comprehensive design of the educational process, the setting of specific goals and their guaranteed achievement, and the realization of the planned result.

The following three psychological principles should be used in the implementation of pedagogical technology:

1. Analysis of individual psychological characteristics of students.
2. Achieving the formation of a system of education and educational relations between the teacher and the student.
3. Ensuring the educational development of the method used in the educational process.

"Method of thinking about music" is aimed at students' personal, individual acquisition of spiritual values. This method involves choosing a problem that can be solved with the help of music and its solution is solved by the students. The following topics can be cited as problem⁴²: "The place of light and serious music in my life"; "What kind of music do modern youth like and why?"; "How is human musical culture manifested?"; "Do Uzbek youth need European classical music?"; "Is pop music a positive thing in the lives of young people?" etc.

References

1. Zakirova, Z. (2023). O‘ZBEK MILLIY MUSIQASINING SHAKLLANISHI VA TARAQQIY ETISH BOSQICHLARI. Interpretation and Researches, 2(1)
2. Azamovna, Z. Z. (2022). From the History of Uzbek National Musical Art. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY, 3(12), 297-301.
3. Azamovna, Z. Z. (2022). Theoretical Foundations of the Formation of Music History. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HISTORY, 3(12), 302-306.
4. Zakirova, Z. A. . (2022). Methods of Using Musical Means in Teaching the History of the Vienna Classical School in the General Educational Process. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 2(4), 95–99.
5. За Закирова [Методика использования музыкальных средств в обучении истории Европы в общеобразовательной школе](#) Science and Education 3 (4), 615-621
6. ZA Zakirova [Methods of using information about the art of music in the teaching of history of Uzbekistan to students of 6–7 grades of secondary schools](#), ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal 11 (10 ...
7. ZA Zakirova [Methods of using information about the art of music in teaching history to students of 9th and 10th grades of secondary schools](#), Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research 10 (10), 1508-1511.
8. ZZ Azamovna, [MUSIC PEDAGOGY SKILLS OF A MUSIC CULTURE TEACHER](#), European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol 8 (4)
9. Z Zakirova, [SCIENTIFIC BASIS FOR INTRODUCING PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MUSIC EDUCATION](#). Theoretical & Applied Science, 69-70

10.ZA Zakirova, ON THE ART OF MUSIC IN TEACHING HISTORY LESSONS TO GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS METHODS AND METHODS OF USE OF RESOURCES. Modern Scientific

Research International Scientific Journal 1 (9), 22-27.

11. PDZZ Azamovna The Role of Music Art in the Cultural and Spiritual Life of Uzbekistan. Texas Journal of Philology, Culture and History 23, 16-19.

12.Tashpulatova, D., & Siddiqova, I. (2021, April). A CRITIQUE OF THE VIEW OF ANTONYMY AS A RELATION BETWEEN WORD FORMS. In *Конференции*.

13.Тошпулатова, Д. Х. (2019). ПОНЯТИЕ И ВИДЫ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ КОНЦЕПЦИЙ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ. АНАЛИЗ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ КОНЦЕПЦИЙ. *Вопросы педагогики*, (7-2), 118-121.

14.ТАШПУЛАТОВА, Д. PRAGMATIC APHORISMS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH FEATURE AND THE PRINCIPLES OF THEIR TRANSMISSION IN THE CORPUS. *СООТНОШЕНИЕ ПАРАЛИНГВИСТИКИ И РЕЧЕВОГО ЭТИКЕТА В РАЗНЫХ ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРАХ*.

15.NAVOI, A., & BABUR, Z. M. (2022). RESEARCH AND EDUCATION.

16.Ташпулатова, Д. Х. К., & Умурзакова, Б. Э. (2023). ПЕРВОНАЧАЛЬНАЯ СИСТЕМА. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 4(ТМА Conference), 303-309.

17.Tashpulatova, D. K. K., & Jiyenbayeva, B. (2023). THE IMPACT OF LEARNING A LANGUAGE ON THE BRAIN FUNCTION. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 4(ТМА Conference), 310-314.